

FRP effects on the strength of Geopolymer Effect of Concrete

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Abstract— Geopolymer concrete could be an alternative of the conventional concrete due their quality and performance in different conditions. In this study, to investigate the effect GFRP on the compressive strength of cube specimen. The specimens were cured in the oven at 60°C 24 hours, and check the effect of GFRP wrapping on the GPC cube specimen through compressive strength test. After the experimental investigation, it is concluded that the compressive strength of cube specimens increases with the wrapping of the GFRP. The compressive strength increases by 40% at 7days test, whereas it increases about 18% after 28 days test. GFRP tensile strength is higher than the GPC specimens. So, it could be used in the repairing and rehabilitation of the structural member. On the experimental results, the compressive strength of GFRP wrapped specimens retains the 37MPa, when GPC specimen strength is 26MPa or 31MPa.

Keywords—Geopolymer concrete; Compressive strength; Mechanical properties; FRP

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is the second most widely used substance in the world, behind water. Sustainable development is critical for the future in the current situation. Natural resources are diminishing at an increasing rate as a result of increased use or demand. River sand is an important component in this segment since it is utilised as fine aggregates in concrete. In the mix design of concrete, m-sand or stone-dust might be a better option to river sand as fine aggregates. When quarry dust is utilised as fine aggregates, the flexural strength of the concrete is better than when river sand is used. [1].

In today's world, geopolymer concrete may be a viable alternative to traditional or Portland cement concrete. Because it employs industrial solid wastes such as flyash, GGBFS, rice husk ash, and sugarcane bagasse ash, geopolymer concrete is environmentally friendly, cost-effective, high-performing, and long-lasting. All pozzolanic materials high in alumina and silica might be employed as binding materials in the GPC [2]. The alkaline solution, which contains sodium or potassium hydroxide and sodium or potassium silicate compounds in a certain ratio, is used to activate the pozzolanic materials. The geopolymerisation reaction happens from the initial fresh condition to the hardened stage in the development of geopolymer concrete, and it comprises numerous phases of the reaction in the mechanism. The geopolymerisation reaction is influenced by a number of parameters, including the pozzolans minerals composition, particle size, sodium or potassium

hydroxide molarity, alkaline ratio, liquid to binder ratio, superplasticizer type, curing kinds, and curing time [3].

The word "geopolymer" was coined by Davidovits in 1978, and it refers to the bonding that occurs after a reaction [4], [5]. In terms of high performance, the SNF-based superplasticiser is optimal for geopolymer concrete, whereas the PCE-based superplasticiser is better for self-compaction in conventional concrete [6], [7]. In the geopolymerisation reaction, the molarity of sodium hydroxide is critical. As a result, increasing the molarity immediately improves the strength of the specimens, but only up to a certain degree. The alkaline ratio is the proportion of sodium silicate to sodium hydroxide, which influences the reaction and impacts the specimen's strength and performance [8]. The flyash-to-GGBFS ratio affects the mechanical characteristics of GPC specimens because the presence of GGBFS in the concrete generates C-S-H bonds, whereas the geopolymer bonds are Na-A-S-H or other comparable. The ideal GGBFS-to-flyash ratio is particularly critical for long-term or durable characteristics [9]. The use of geopolymer concrete reduces the amount of water in the concrete and boosts the specimen's strength. For geopolymerisation reactions, the liquid-to-binder ratio is also particularly effective. As a result, a liquid limit is critical for the specimens to build strength. In the flyash-slag-based geopolymer concrete, the liquid-to-binder ratio is determined to be optimal at 0.6 [10]. The geopolymer concrete highly resistant in durability parameters like acid attack, sulphate attack than the conventional concrete [11].

FRP composites are a subset of the composites class of materials. The FRP composite is primarily composed of two materials: high-strength fiber reinforcement and a liquid polymer, resulting in a solid, inhomogeneous, and anisotropic construction material. FRP composites also contain additives, the primary goal of which is to protect the composite's surface against corrosive, damp, or fire-hazardous situations. Unidirectional (rovings for glass fibers and tow for carbon fibers), chopped fiber mats, woven textiles, and non-crimp fabrics are among the many reinforcing materials available. These kinds were created with simplicity of fabrication and mechanical qualities in mind [12], [13].

A fiber is a long filament formed of a single substance, such as glass, carbon, or aramid. The fiber's primary functions include providing appropriate strength and stiffness, carrying the imposed load, and generating thermal stability, among others. To achieve this, the fiber must have certain features,

such as a suitable modulus of elasticity and ultimate strength, minimum fluctuation in strength, fiber stability while handling, and fiber diameter homogeneity. The backbone of the fiber and the structure of the molecule both influence the fiber's qualities. Furthermore, the fibers must have an adequate aspect ratio in more than one direction, i.e., they must offer a reinforcing function in both the longitudinal and transversal directions. The performance of the FRP composite is frequently degraded throughout the manufacturing process. Glass fibers are an example of this, since they have the drawback of being extremely sensitive to even minor faults, which can result in a significant drop in strength. Controlling and consequently removing defects throughout the manufacturing process is one way to avoid this. The fiber modulus, on the other hand, remains unaffected throughout manufacturing, resulting in an accurate modulus prediction. Fibers are made either by drawing from a melt, as in the case of glass fibers, or as precursors, as in the case of carbon fibers, by spinning extrusions for chemical or thermal conversion.

Fibers and matrix are the two main components of composites. The fibers account for 30 to 70 percent of the composite's volume and 50 percent of its weight. Fibers' primary tasks are to transport weight and offer stiffness, strength, thermal stability, and other structural qualities to FRP. High modulus of elasticity, high ultimate strength, minimal fluctuation in strength among fibers, great strength stability during handling, and high homogeneity of diameter and surface dimension among fibers are all requirements for FRP composites. The matrix guarantees that the fibers are in the right place and aligned, that the composite is protected from damage during manufacturing and manipulation, that the composite is durable, and that the composite is protected from environmental influences. It's also in charge of distributing the loads throughout the different fibres. carbon, glass, and aramid fibers are among the most common forms of fiber used in civil engineering projects.

Fiber Reinforced Polymers (FRP) are being used in a wide range of civil engineering applications in recent years. Reinforced concrete constructions are also strengthened using this material. The capacity of structural members to withstand extra loads induced by changes in live load, design mistake, age of structure, and other factors necessitates strengthening of concrete structures [14], [15].

Glass fiber is by far the most common and versatile fiber used in the reinforced polymer sector. Glass fibers are employed in a variety of ways in reinforced concrete buildings. AR-glass is a zirconium silicate-based alkali-resistant glass. It can withstand the alkaline climate present in concrete, but it is significantly more expensive. In Portland cement substrates, it's used. x E-glass — Alkali-free, high-electrical-resistance glass manufactured from alumina-calcium borosilicate. Because of its strength and electrical resistance, e-glass is referred to as a general-purpose fiber in the industry. In the FRP composite sector, it is the most often used fiber. x S-glass — Magnesium aluminosilicate glass with high strength. When high strength, stiffness, severe temperature resistance, and corrosive resistance are required, this material is used. By far the most popular and least priced is e-glass.

Strapping and filament tapes have tensile strengths ranging from 100 to 600 pounds per inch of width. Filament tape backings are often constructed of transparent plastic or brown paper, with filaments running lengthwise down the tape to provide strength [16], [17].

The oven-drying curing specimens generated 90% of the 28-day compressive strength at 3 days, whereas the ambient curing specimens attained 57–82%; nevertheless, the ultimate strength of the ambient curing specimens was somewhat more remarkable than the matching oven-drying cured specimens at 28 days. After 7 days, the rate of increase in compressive strength in oven-cured specimens is not noteworthy [18].

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Experimental program includes the materials preliminary testing, mixing, casting, curing and tests setups.

Table 1 Chemical Composition

Minerals	Flyash	GGBFS
Silica (SiO ₂)	45.8	34.52
Alumina (Al ₂ O ₃)	21.4	20.66
Lime (CaO)	13.7	32.43
Iron Oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	12.6	.57
Magnesia (MgO)	1.3	10.09
Sulphate (SO ₃)	1.9	0.77
LOI*	0.1	0.3

LOI*- Loss of Ignition

A. Materials

This section describes the raw materials properties after the preliminary testing. Flyash, GGBFS, Coarse aggregates, fine aggregates, sodium hydroxide, sodium silicate, superplasticiser and water are the basic raw materials were used in the mix design of GPC.

Table 1 depicts the mineral composition of the flyash and GGBFS. The mineral oxides those were presented in the flyash and GGBFS found through the x-ray fluorescence test. Class-c flyash were used in the mix design. Fig.1a and Fig.1b shows the SEM pictures of the flyash and GGBFS particles. It describes that the flyash is hollow and spherical in shape whereas the GGBFS is irregular. Fig.1c shows the XRD graph of flyash and GGBFS which shows that the amorphous nature of both. Sodium hydroxide and sodium silicate are used as alkaline activator in the mix design of GPC, and both are purchased from the market that are manufactured by the CDH pvt ltd. Delhi. The sodium hydroxide has 98% of minimum purity, whereas the sodium silicate is alkaline in nature. The SNF-based superplasticiser is used in mix design that are manufacture by the Fosroc chemicals. It is also called as SP Conplast 430.

Locally available stone dust is used as fine aggregates, whereas the 10mm and 20mm size coarse were used in the mix design of the GPC. The preliminary tests were conducted on both types of aggregates, to check the quality of the aggregates. The stone-dust is found in zone-2 and well-graded after the preliminary tests conducted on the stone dust,

whereas the sand also found in the Zone II but it poorly graded. Fig.1d depicts the gradation curve of both river sand and stone-dust, which shows that both are well-graded. The fineness modulus, specific gravity, water absorption, silt content, and bulk density of the stone-dust are 2.756, 2.62, 1.21%, 6%, and 1610kg/m³, respectively [19]–[24]. The fineness modulus, specific gravity, water absorption, crushing value, impact value, flakiness index, elongation index, and abrasion value of the coarse aggregates are 7.29, 2.79, .2%, 23%, 22%, 24%, 30%, and 8%, respectively. Table 2 depicts the properties of river sand and stone-dust after the preliminary tests conducted on both in the laboratory. Table 3 depicts the properties of coarse aggregates used in the mix.

Glass FRP is used in the experimental analysis of the GPC mix specimens. Fig.2e shows the picture of glass FRP sample. This GPC cube specimens wrapped by the GFRP, and check the effectiveness of that.

Table 2 Properties of stone-dust and river sand

Test	River-sand	Stone-dust
Zone	Zone-II	Zone II
Grade	Poor graded	well graded
Fineness modulus	2.587	2.756 (medium sand)
Specific gravity	2.63	2.62
Water absorption	.43%	1.21 %
Silt content	0.2%	6 %
Bulk density	1596kg/m ³	1610 kg/m ³

Table 3 Properties of coarse aggregates

Test	Results
Fineness modulus	7.29
Specific gravity	2.79
Water absorption	0.2%
Crushing value	23%
Impact value	22%
Flakiness index	24%
Elongation index	30%
Abrasion value	8%

B. Mixing, Casting, and Curing

This section describes the mixing procedure, casting in different moulds samples and their curing type and duration. The mixing of the raw materials in the pan mixture for 10-15minutes. **Table 4** depicts the raw materials content are used in the mix design of the GPC. The alkaline solution is made 20-24 hours before the mixing. After the mixing, the fresh

concrete were tests for the workability, and after casted in the different mould samples. The three Types of specimens were made for the mechanical strength evaluation are as cube, cylinder, and prism shape as per the Indian Standard. The curing of the specimens was conducted in the oven at 60°C for 4 hours to 72 hours.

Table 4 Mix Design of GPC

Material	Quantity (kg/m ³)
Flyash	303.75
GGBFS	101.25
Coarse Aggregates (20mm)	761
Coarse Aggregates (10mm)	508
Fine Aggregates/Stone dust	683
Sodium Hydroxide	46.28
Sodium silicate	115.72
Superplasticiser	4.05
Water	20.25

C. Tests Setups

All the experiments are conducted on the GPC mix on fresh stage or hardened form in the concrete laboratory.

The density is used to assess the chemical properties of GPC mix samples. Before the 28-day destructive inspection, the weight of cube samples is used to test the density of the mix design.

The GPC mix designs cubic samples of dimension 150mm*150mm*150mm are used to test the compressive strength of the specimens. The samples were tested in an axial loading mode on a Universal Testing Machine at a loading rate of 5.2kN/sec.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The density and compressive strength tests were conducted on the specimens after 7 days, 14days and 28 days of casting. The compressive strength is measured both time before and after wrapping of the GFRP.

A. Density

The density of the GPC specimens found 2440kg/m³ after the evaluation from tests. The density is calculated through the weight of cube specimens. **Fig.1** shows the picture during the weight of cube specimen.

Figure 1 Picture during weight

B. Compressive Strength

The compressive strength of geopolymer concrete specimens test after 7 days, 14 days, and 28 days of casting. The GPC specimen's tests in the CTM for compressive strength of both type of specimens. The GPC specimens with or without wrapped with the GFRP tested at same day and compare them. The compressive strength of the GPC increases with the wrapping of the GFRP on the specimens. Fig.2 shows the graph of compressive strength variation with the age of concrete of both type of specimens. The compressive strength increases by 40% at 7days test, whereas it increases about 18% after 28 days test.

Figure 2 Graph of Compressive strength

IV. CONCLUSIONS

After the experimental investigation in the laboratory, the following conclusions are as follows:

- Initially tests conducted on the raw materials and found that the fine aggregate is well aggregate, flyash is class c type. The flyash particle is spherical porous in nature whereas the GGBFS has irregular shape.

- The compressive strength of the GPC increases with the wrapping of the GFRP on the specimens. The compressive strength increases by 40% at 7days test, whereas it increases about 18% after 28 days test.

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